

NAVIGATING UPSKILLING AND EMPLOYMENT CAPABILITY OF STUDENTPRENEURS FOR LOCAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN AN INNOVATION-FOCUSED UNIVERSITY

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Abstract

The paper explores the importance of entrepreneurial upskilling and employment capability of studentpreneurs for local economic development at the Federal University of Technology, Akure (FUTA), Nigeria, an innovation-focused university. The paper highlights policy inputs into entrepreneurship education with a view to ameliorating employment generation for wealth and economic prosperity in Nigeria. The paper adopts a quantitative, cross-sectional approach on a sample size of 130 studentpreneurs chosen from the repository of studentpreneurs in the Centre for Entrepreneurship (CENT) through non-probabilistic purposive and convenience techniques responsible for coordinating practical skills in entrepreneurship required to establish and successfully manage enterprises by undergraduate students of FUTA. The outcome of the study reveals that, more than 70% of the studentpreneurs claim to achieve entrepreneurial upskilling through their personal initiatives. Some of the studentpreneurs acknowledge their sources of entrepreneurial upskilling as entrepreneurship education (58%); entrepreneurship enlightenment programme (EEP) (49%); entrepreneurship training by skill/enterprise (46%); students' entrepreneurial ideation/pitching competition (37%); enterprise start-up/enterprise incubation competition (36%); and students' entrepreneurial mentorship/accelerator programme (32%). The study reveals that entrepreneurial upskilling significantly ($\chi^2=186.352$, $p\leq 0.05$) influences employment capability of the FUTA studentpreneurs to create wealth, economic prosperity as well as sustainable development for Nigeria. The paper concludes that entrepreneurial upskilling for employment capability is germane for fashioning opportunity mindsets that can translate to national development of the "next-generation (NextGen) entrepreneurs in Nigeria. The study offers policy options for the government to improve entrepreneurship support and offer advice to committed NextGen entrepreneurs to succeed, shape a better future and achieve rapid economic development for Nigeria.

Keywords: *Studentpreneurs, Upskilling, Employability, NextGen, Economic development*

1.0 Introduction

The global relevance of a nation is increasingly dependent on creating new enterprise opportunities, stimulating investments through entrepreneurship to meet the changing demands of the society for employability, and improving national economic development. Economic development is vital for addressing unemployment and economic challenges faced by developing

nations (Bardales-Cárdenas *et al.*, 2024). The concept through entrepreneurial upskilling and employment capability building has continued to gain global attention at regional, national and state levels. Entrepreneurship programmes especially in higher educational institutions (HEIs) integrate experiential learning, such as start-up incubation and industry mentorship translating into practical experience from theoretical knowledge that enhances employability. According to the British Council (2018), employability is the possession of knowledge, aptitudes, skills and other traits required by employers. Hence, the subjects of entrepreneurship, entrepreneurship education, skill acquisition and upskilling have become increasingly important for the recovery of socio-economic development faced by developing economies.

From another perspective, entrepreneurial skills are knowledge and abilities that recognise and exploit consumers' needs as well as technological and commercial opportunities (Ojo *et al.*, 2022; Dada & Asaolu, 2023). Entrepreneurial skill is one of the most important components in motivating the NextGen to undertake enterprise engagement. The knowledge acquired and attitudes of the youths towards entrepreneurial skills do influence their inclination to set their own business (Ojo *et al.*, 2023). Entrepreneurs invest in developing their entrepreneurial skills and upskills through career development programmes, mentorship programmes, and online courses that cover the basics of business management, business planning, and business analysis as part of their decision making. These skills include technical, financial, marketing, interpersonal, leadership and managerial skills. Entrepreneurial skills are the knowledge and aptitudes to recognise and take advantage of market, technical or customer opportunities (Oladele *et al.*, 2022). The acquisition of entrepreneurial skills has been a global focus on the abilities of young people to succeed in the dynamic digital age. The entrepreneurial skills could help young people to acquire experience and develop business opportunities that would increase their employability potential to create jobs and be self-reliant rather than seeking wage employment. The connection between entrepreneurial skill buildings and local economic development has been the subject of growing interest in academia and society which affects the success of academic and business innovation (Wang & Fu, 2023; Bardales-Cárdenas *et al.*, 2024).

In the African sub-region, some countries including Nigeria have experienced sustained economic growth in the last decade without corresponding improvement in employment capability of the next generation (NextGen). The contemporary needs to generate employment, create wealth, alleviate poverty, combat diseases and improve the quality of life of the citizenry have been compounded by the advent of globalization, innovation deficit as well as global competitiveness. This complexities of the 21st century, marked by rapid technological advancements and unprecedented global challenges, demand a departure from conventional thinking especially among the NextGen of Higher Educational Institutions (HEIs). The critical importance of entrepreneurship for wealth creation, employment generation, poverty alleviation as well as economic recovery and growth keeps attracting the attention of industrial actors, policymakers and scholars, especially in the HEIs (Dada & Asaolu, 2023; Olu-Alonge & Dada, 2025).

The aim of entrepreneurship education and skill acquisition is to build the knowledge of the HEIs' NextGen for accelerating enterprise development and self-employability, leading to sustainable economic development and prosperity. The entrepreneurship education and skill acquisition in the HEIs among the NextGen improve the standard of training in the industrial sector in response to labour market needs as well as improvement in the management strategies of university entrepreneurship and innovation activities (Dada *et al.*, 2021). One of the strategies for building entrepreneurial skills is upskilling which is the process of acquiring new skills or upgrading existing ones to improve performance, productivity and career prospects. Upskilling involves learning new technologies, techniques and methodologies to stay relevant in a rapidly

changing work environment and competitive job market. Upskilling is a way to level up individuals' current skill sets, perform more effectively and efficiently in current job description and prepare in advance into new roles. Entrepreneurial upskilling involves enhancing current skills or acquiring new ones to advance in a specific field or adapt to emerging trends. Upskilling involves building on existing knowledge such as learning advanced data analytics for a marketing professional to generate growth opportunities internally and stay competitive (Dada, 2025).

As a strategy to contribute to entrepreneurial skills, upskilling is relevant for entrepreneurship programmes to enhance the capacities of business, entrepreneurship and innovation to develop and deliver industrial sustainable innovation-driven programmes. By leveraging numerous methods to acquire the necessary skills and knowledge, entrepreneurs can effectively navigate the competitive environment and leverage their entrepreneurial skills, essential technology and interpersonal skills to drive enterprise growth, navigate challenges and maximize their potential for success. Embracing growth mindsets, entrepreneurial upskilling and life-long learning ensures continuous growth and the ability to adapt to changing marketing models and business drivers. Thus, harnessing the entrepreneurial skills of HEI's NextGen requires a combination of educational approaches, financial support, networks, and appropriate policies among stakeholders to achieve substantial impact on local economic development. Consequently, this study has been undertaken to determine the entrepreneurial upskilling of studentpreneurs of the Federal University of Technology, Akure (FUTA), Nigeria for the advancement of employment capability and sustainable development. The aim of the paper is to better equip the HEIs in building entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystems, leading to increased sustainable industrial development, economic growth and prosperity in Nigeria. The paper therefore argues that applications of upskilling can revitalise Nigeria's industrial sector and offer policy suggestions that can transform Nigeria into a healthy industrial economy. The paper provides actionable policy recommendations to support the strategy for activating entrepreneurial and innovative mindsets of the NextGen for building entrepreneurial ecosystems in HEIs. This can contribute to employment generation strategy and government action plans on increasing self-employability of HEIs' NextGen for sustainable industrial development, economic growth and prosperity in Nigeria.

2.0 Review of Related Literature

The paper reviews some related literature in this section. These include the concept of entrepreneurship, higher education institutions (HEIs) and entrepreneurship education, entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial skill building, upskilling and employment capability; and concept of local economic development (LED).

2.1 Concept of Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship is a dynamic process of vision, change, and creation (Lufiana *et al.*, 2023). It requires an application of energy and passion towards the creation and implementation of new ideas and a creative situation. Nwafor *et al.* (2021) defines entrepreneurship as the readiness to develop, organise and run a business enterprise along with any of its uncertainties to make profit. Entrepreneurship encapsulates the attitude, skills and actions of an individual or individuals starting a new business and it is the most prevalent and potent economic force on a global scale (Akinbode & Oyelude, 2020). Entrepreneurship is the art or science of innovation and risk taking, creative thinking to identify market opportunities, acquire resources, and adapt to the environment for the purpose of making profit in business (Qwabe *et al.*, 2025). Entrepreneurship

is the act of founding a business, negotiating commercial deals as well as taking risks in order to profit from the education-related abilities attained (Obamuyi *et al.*, 2022).

It is essential for an entrepreneurial society and culture to have the entrepreneurial spirit in order to obtain desired results (Akinbode & Oyelude, 2020). Entrepreneurial spirit is a means by which an individual is willing and capable of looking for investment possibilities, developing and successfully running a business entrepreneurial spirit (Ojo *et al.*, 2022). According to Ojeifo (2013), entrepreneurship is the willingness and ability of a person, business, or organisation to recognise a trend in the environment and take advantage of the chance to generate goods and services for the general public. Entrepreneurship is a manner of thinking, reasoning and doing things that is opportunity oriented, holistic in approach, and balanced in terms of leadership.

In emerging and developed economies, entrepreneurship has played vital roles in contributing significantly to employment creation, innovative technologies and enterprises, improved business models and economic growth (Rajamani *et al.*, 2022). Entrepreneurs often bring fresh perspectives, innovative ideas, and creative solutions to problems through new technologies and social change. Entrepreneurship is a crucial strategy for fostering innovation, competition, job creation and economic development. It is an individual's creative ability to identify and establish investment opportunities in the environment based on knowledge and the act of engaging in business, finance, and invention for the purpose of producing economic goods (Garba, 2016). This is also a process that involves an individual's effort in locating viable business opportunities in a given environment as well as acquiring and overseeing the resources required to take advantage of those opportunities (Akpojotor, 2024). Similar to this, Ferreira (2019) believes that entrepreneurship deals with the human activity of creating business to bring forth profits.

Entrepreneurship refers to the processes that lead to the emergence, behaviour, and performance of entrepreneurs. It is a concentration on the steps to start a new organisation, behaviour and performance as measured by profit levels. It makes them capable of assimilating into society and making a positive impact on its economic growth. This demonstrates how an effective educational institution considers the dynamics of the labour market and provides its graduates with professional skills and abilities to help them become independent (Ojeifo, 2013). Entrepreneurship is the capacity of some individuals to take on risk and combine factors of production in order to produce commodities and services (Shahriar, 2018). It is also a person's motivation and capacity to look for investment opportunities in a given setting and their capacity to successfully launch and manage a business based on the prospects found (Chinwendu, 2024). However, because entrepreneurship does not take place in a vacuum, it is linked to a variety of other activities. It necessitates the existence of an entrepreneur and a supportive setting (Akpojotor, 2024). Entrepreneurship is faced with uncertainties as emerging entrepreneurs to start a new business in order to set a challenge when starting a new firm and setting ambitious goals (Wang & Wong, 2004; Shahriar, 2018). The interests of young graduates always increase towards an entrepreneurial career through adequate knowledge acquired from entrepreneurship education (Wang & Wong, 2004; Wang, 2020; Obamuyi *et al.*, 2022).

2.2 Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and Entrepreneurship Education

Despite the policy implementation of entrepreneurship programmes in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) over decades, many graduates in Nigeria still face the problem of unemployment and unrestrained job seeking as opposed to job creation. It is therefore essential to nurture the spirit of entrepreneurship and innovation in this age of rapid technological change and global competition among undergraduates, especially in technology-based institutions (Dada,

2020; Obamuyi *et al.*, 2022). The government's approach to solving the problem of unemployment in Nigeria has historically been unmindful of the potential role of entrepreneurial education despite many attempts to formulate policies and/or programmes to support employment generation in Nigeria. This might have contributed to the high level of unemployment in the country; and might have informed the initiative by the National Universities Commission (NUC) to introduce entrepreneurial studies into the curricula of Nigerian Universities in 2006.

Entrepreneurship education had been part of polytechnics' curricula before this period which is being coordinated by the National Board for Technical Education (NBTE). Polytechnics are supposed to provide practical skills in diverse areas to tackle the skills gap in industry. Teaching and mentoring students in practical entrepreneurial orientation justifies the continuous relevance of polytechnic education within Nigeria's higher education system. Therefore, polytechnic engagement in applied and experimental research becomes necessary to generate new knowledge, products and processes needed to promote industrial growth. The recent agitation for conversion of polytechnics to universities, as done in the USA, UK and Singapore, for instance, can only be justified for those that have shown adequate competencies and capabilities in research, innovation and knowledge advancement.

2.3 Entrepreneurship Education and Entrepreneurial Skill Building

Entrepreneurship education is about learners developing the skills and mindset to be able to turn creative ideas into entrepreneurial action (Ojah, 2023; Qwabe *et al.*, 2025). Empirical evidence and the findings of numerous research supported the need to establish entrepreneurship development centres (EDCs) of all the higher educational institutions (HEIs) in Nigeria in order to address the issue of youth unemployment and increase the undergraduate entrepreneurial mindset. As a result, post-secondary institutions are fast integrating entrepreneurship education into their curricula in an effort to inform and prepare future graduates to choose alternative career paths rather than apply for white-collar employment following graduation (Cui *et al.*, 2019; Dada, 2024). Ojeifo (2013) describes entrepreneurship as the willingness and capability of a person, business or organisation to recognise a change in the environment and take advantage of the opportunity to produce goods and services for the general public. Olorundare and Kayode (2014) use a qualitative technique to conduct research on entrepreneurship education and its applicability for Nigerian University graduates. They conclude that every university in Nigeria should have a centre for entrepreneurship education and undergraduate students should participate in internship programmes with successful entrepreneurs for at least two months.

Akpojotor (2024) also uses a qualitative approach to conduct a study on entrepreneurship education among young people, particularly students in higher institutions in Nigeria. The researcher suggests that educational programmes at all levels of schooling be tailored to provide young people with necessary business skills and that the Nigerian government should give full-blown entrepreneurial education the attention it deserves. Salihu (2016) observes that graduates in North Central Nigeria started new businesses after receiving entrepreneurship education. The researcher concludes that graduates' expectations for an entrepreneurial career have a big impact on how they establish their own businesses. He stresses that tertiary institutions and the government should take a more proactive role by coming up with a plan to help students who show interest in starting businesses while they are still in school and after they graduate through incubator programmes to encourage graduates' career aspirations towards business start-up and further serve as motivation for graduates' entrepreneurial attitudes toward self-employment. Oladele *et al.* (2022) investigate the Students' Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES) on Technological Entrepreneurship Interest in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The study

reveals SIWES as a source of upskilling for entrepreneurship education earlier received by the students in higher education institutions. The study offers some managerial recommendations for all parties involved in entrepreneurship education and makes recommendations for future research.

2.4 Upskilling and Employment capability

Upskilling is the process by which individuals acquire new or upgrade existing skills to improve their performance, efficiency as well as outputs. Upskilling involves learning new technologies, techniques, and methodologies to favourably compete in a changing global economy. The importance of upskilling includes enhanced production, new employability prospects, increased income generations, boosted professional outlook, efficiency and effectiveness, improved adaptability, competitive advantage, sense of accomplishment and personal growth (Dada, 2024). Different types of upskilling are business upskilling, creative upskilling, soft-skills upskilling and technical upskilling. Each upskilling supports the operations and efficiencies of an enterprise for improved performance in the form of improved turnover, increased market share, wealth creations, employment generation, social benefits as well as an eco-friendly environment. An individual can upskill through personal exploitation, attendance of workshops and conferences, online courses, mentorship, extensive reading of books, articles, and blogs to acquire new skills and knowledge, and on-the-job training. There has been increasing global concern over the continuous rapid expansion of unemployment in the developing countries that the youths have been identified as the most affected groups (Chinwendu, 2024).

However, it is expected that such graduates would possess some innovative skills gained as a result of entrepreneurship education for technology-based enterprise formation that assures the development of wealth, jobs and economic returns in the country (Dada et al., 2021; Ojo et al., 2023). The dearth of entrepreneurial career intention and preference for self-employability have been recognized as major contributing factors to the problem of unemployment of graduates and youths in Nigeria (Dada, 2022; Chinwendu, 2024). Therefore, increasing numbers of graduates in Nigeria face the challenges of employability (Akinbode & Oyelude, 2020; Ojo et al., 2023).

2.5 Concept of Local Economic Development

Local economic development (LED) is a process of partnership among public organisations, private sector and communities to effectively mobilise, manage and capitalise resources into economic ventures in order to promote sustainable growth and development (Ngobeni et al., 2025). Local economic development involves the stimulation and development of well-being and working conditions of ecosystems to stimulate new employment, create wealth and generate income (Kahika & Karyeija, 2017). LED is a process that is managed by the public organisation through a constitutional obligation to improve local communities (Mokoena, 2019). Enaigoghe and Ramsuraj's (2023) findings support the notion that entrepreneurs and SMEs are important drivers of local economic development. Ngobeni et al. (2025) therefore, posit that LED can be employed to encourage the NextGen to establish their enterprises to address the high unemployment rate, high poverty level, low income and low level of skills causing poor economic growth and development. LED therefore encourages entrepreneurship through pitching, campaigns, entrepreneurship education, skills acquisitions to strengthen the enabling environment and enhances access to finance and markets.

Studies on the local economic development, employment capability and entrepreneurial upskilling are becoming prominent to address the social and economic challenges facing

developing economies. Local economic development is a participatory process to build up the economic capacity of a local area in order to improve its economic future and the quality of life for all (Roche, 2018). Local economic development initiatives usually start with identifying the relevant stakeholders that are included in decision-making processes. Through Local economic development, public, industry, and non-governmental actors interact and work collectively to create better conditions for economic growth and employment generation (Clark *et al.*, 2010). Local economic development is strategically planned to strengthen the local economic capacity of an area, improve the investment climate, and increase the productivity and competitiveness of local businesses, entrepreneurs and workers (Kanayo *et al.*, 2021). LEDs can improve the quality of life, create new economic opportunities to strategically change and increase the competitive market economy.

Local economic development is a participatory process where actors within the HEIs can work together to stimulate profitable venture activities resulting in a resilient and sustainable economy (Awad & Salaimah, 2023). It helps to create decent jobs and improve the quality of life for everyone to find solutions to common economic challenges such as unemployment among graduates. The local economic development process seeks to empower local participants in order to effectively utilize business enterprise, labour, capital and other resources to achieve priorities (for instance, promote quality jobs, reduce poverty, stabilize the economy, and provide better services). Local economic development makes important contributions to national economic performance; hence it has become more critical with increased global competition, technological advances and employment generation for economic growth and development. Local economic development can offer significant benefits to foster enterprise creation and entrepreneurship culture especially among youths with new employment opportunities (Apostol, 2022).

3.0 Methodology

A pragmatic paradigm is adopted, whereby the researchers understand the realities of the employability situation in Nigeria and make decisions based on thorough research. The study employed the mixed research method (MRM), a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods. A survey research technique was conducted among the third to fifth level students who had undergone practical skills in entrepreneurship (ENT 302) across the eleven Schools (Faculties) in the FUTA. Using a non-probabilistic approach, purposive and snowball sampling technique was used to elicit data from the students who had established their enterprises (Studentpreneurs) after the entrepreneurship training programme. A set of questionnaires was administered to 103 studentpreneur while personal interviews were conducted on selected respondents who had distinguished themselves in their enterprises. All selected studentpreneurs (100%) responded because the questionnaire was administered on them at a location during a TETFund-Sponsored training for the student entrepreneurs at a location in FUTA. The studentpreneurs are registered with the Centre for Entrepreneurship (CENT) that is responsible for creating entrepreneurial mindsets and entrepreneurial spirits in FUTA graduates; reduce phobia for self-employment; and prepare the graduates for business policy formulation and entrepreneurial skills necessary for national development. The Centre for Entrepreneurship, FUTA also, through various approaches creates in students the culture of entrepreneurship to prepare them for value-creation, employment generation and self-employment which can result in wealth creation for individuals and national transformation. The building of entrepreneurial alertness and culture involves some steps during the ENT 302 programme among the level three students (Dada, 2020). Descriptive statistics such as percentage, frequency counts, mean, charts; and inferential statistics such as regression analysis and analysis of variance (ANOVA) were employed for data analysis.

4.0 Results and Discussion

This section presents the results and discusses the outcome of the study. These include some socio-economic characteristics of the respondents such as gender dispersion of the studentpreneurs, academic levels of the studentpreneurs, students' distributions by Schools/Faculties, classifications of business engagements of the studentpreneurs, types of multiple upskilling engaged by the studentpreneurs, sources of entrepreneurial upskilling of the studentpreneurs as well as the influence of entrepreneurial upskilling on employment capability of the studentpreneurs.

4.1 Gender Dispersion of the Studentpreneurs

The gender dispersion of the studentpreneurs is shown in Figure 1 which reveals that most (71.24%) of the student entrepreneurs are male. The cause of the high ratio of male studentpreneurs may be due to the belief that males are often more energetic than their female counterparts and are conscious of their present and future family responsibilities (Shahriar, 2018; Obamuyi *et al.*, 2022).

Figure 1: Gender Dispersion of the Studentpreneurs (N=103)

Moreso, women entrepreneurs with innovative ideas are usually faced with several challenges. For instance, Olu-Alonge and Dada (2025) found that stringent investment environments such as access to finance, insecurity and electricity tariff hike greatly affect young women entrepreneurs in Ekiti State. Similarly, Igwe et al. (2018) found that lack of access to a range of affordable, safe and reliable financial services is a great challenge to business owners in Nigeria.

4.2 Academic Levels of the Studentpreneurs

Figure 2 depicts the distributions of the Studentpreneurs by their academic levels. Majority (86.7%) of the student entrepreneurs were in their level three. The high proportion of level three students is not unconnected with the fact that they are the latest set to complete the practical skills in the entrepreneurship (ENT 302) training programme that entrenches entrepreneurial knowledge in all undergraduate students. The entrepreneurial development centre programme has since created entrepreneurial mindsets and entrepreneurial spirits in FUTA graduates; and reduced phobia for self-employment among the graduates. The Centre also prepares the students for business policy formulation and entrepreneurial skills necessary to become outstanding entrepreneurs or intrapreneurs for national development (Dada, 2020).

Figure 2: Distributions of the Studentpreneurs by Academic Levels (N=103)

The least (3.25%) number of the student entrepreneurs may not be unconnected with the fact that most of them are currently engaged with their final year project and they need to concentrate on their studies towards graduation.

4.3 Distribution of Studentpreneurs by Schools (Faculties)

The distribution of the Studentpreneurs by School (Faculty) is depicted in Table 1. The Table revealed that most of the Studentpreneurs were drawn from Schools of Infrastructural, Minerals and Manufacturing Engineering (20.39%), Electrical Systems Engineering (17.48%), Computing (15.53%), Agriculture and Agricultural Technology (12.62%); and Physical Sciences (10.68%).

The high proportion of studentpreneurs from these Schools (Faculties) may not be unconnected with the high creative and innovative manner of these courses of study. The insignificant number of the studentpreneurs were found in the Schools of Earth and Mineral Science (1.94%), Health and Health Technology (3.88%), Logistics and Innovation Technology (4.86%), Life Sciences (5.83%); and Environmental Technology (6.79%).

Table 1: Distribution of Studentpreneurs by Schools (Faculties) (N = 103)

School (Faculty)	Frequency	Percent
Infrastructural, Minerals and Manufacturing Engineering	21	20.39
Electrical Systems Engineering	18	17.48
Computing	16	15.53
Agriculture and Agricultural Technology	13	12.62
Physical Sciences	11	10.68
Environmental Technology	7	6.79
Life Sciences	6	5.83
Logistics and Innovation Technology	5	4.86
Health and Health Technology	4	3.88
Earth and Mineral Sciences	2	1.94
Total	103	100

4.4 Classifications of Business Engagements of the Studentpreneurs

The classifications of business engagements of the studentpreneurs are as shown in Figure 3. Majority (36.36%) of the enterprises were digitally-based to include software development, digital marketing, website designing, AutoCAD design, digital photography/photoshop services. The high proportion of digitally-based enterprises may be due to the awareness of the high level of information technology among the new generation.

Moreover, 20.83% of the enterprises were creative-based such as fashion designing/knitting, digital photography/photoshop services, leather product enterprises like bags, shoes, entertainment enterprises. Those enterprises in service-based (19.85%) include electrical installations and fittings, furnishing, carpentry, engineering fabrications, laundering services, confectionery and catering services. The enterprises engaged under agriculture-based (13.29%) were fish production and processing, poultry production, crop production and processing. The enterprises engaged

under manufacturing-based (9.67%) by the Studentpreneurs were paint production, wood processing, bio-ethanol production, waste recycling/wealth creation from waste.

Figure 3: Classification of the Studentpreneurs by Enterprise-Based (N = 103), Source: Studentpreneurs Survey, 2025

Types of Multiple Upskilling Engaged by the Studentpreneurs

The types of upskilling engaged in multiple forms by the studentpreneurs is depicted in Figure 4. The Figure revealed that the types of upskilling include soft/smart skills upskilling (81.67%) that are particularly relevant for industrial growth such as artificial intelligence (AI), the internet of things (IoT), drones' skills. The soft-skills involve the development of non-technical skills like problem-solving skills to overcome challenges and develop innovative solutions to be able to think critically and make informed decisions. Other soft-skills upskilling are effective communication skills essential for building relationships, pitching ideas, and leading teams through clear and persuasive communication. The studentpreneurs also engaged in the upskilling of soft-skills in the form of professional networking needed for active participation in enterprise activities to connect with professionals and open new opportunities and valuable insights. The professional networking strengthens connections and participation in industrial actions and mentorship programmes.

**Multiple Responses

Figure 4: Types of Upskilling Engaged by the Studentpreneurs (N=103)

Moreover, the studentpreneurs claimed to engage in technical upskilling (70.49%) in the form of acquisition of new technical skills like digital skills, programming languages, advanced materials, AutoCAD design, digital printing. The technical upskilling is essential for navigating the digital landscape, including data analytics and digital marketing. The business upskilling was claimed by 64.81% of the studentpreneurs to learn entrepreneurial-related skills in business plan development, business and innovation analytics, business communication, financial and record-keeping, marketing and advertising, leadership and social influence, collaboration and outsourcing, human resource management, penetration, finance, production, project management, waste recycling/wealth creation from waste, soap, detergent and cream production, confectionery and catering services. This outcome corroborates with the results obtained from the research conducted on small scale enterprises and youth empowerment in Nigeria by Okoye (2024). The studentpreneurs also engaged in creative upskilling (57.13%) which involves development of creative skills such as fashion designing/knitting, digital photography/photoshop services, leatherwork like bags, shoes, website designing, AutoCAD design/digital printing, photography, and videography.

4.5 Sources of Entrepreneurial Upskilling of the Studentpreneurs

Table 2 depicts the sources of entrepreneurial upskilling of the studentpreneurs in the Federal University of Technology, Akure, Nigeria. The Table discloses that the majority of the respondents claimed their sources of entrepreneurial upskilling as technology and automation

(97.73%), entrepreneurship education and lifelong learning (95.72%), collaboration/professional networking (94.63%); and design thinking (92.81%).

Table 2: Sources of Entrepreneurial Upskilling of the Studentpreneurs (N = 103)

Source of Upskilling**	Percent
Technology and Automation (TA, n =102)	97.73
Entrepreneurship Education and Lifelong Learning (EELL, n =101)	95.72
Collaboration/Professional Networking (CPN, n =97)	94.63
Design Thinking (DT, n = 96)	92.81
Entrepreneurial Mentorship and Accelerator Programme (EMAP, n =101)	90.24
Personal Entrepreneurial Exploits/Experience (PEEE, n =103)	86.54
Entrepreneurship Development/Enlightenment Programme (EDEP, n= 91)	82.44
Enterprise Start-up Pitching (ESP, n = 87)	75.93
Enterprise Skill Training (EST, n = 98)	71.92

***Multiple Responses*

Source: Studentpreneurs Survey, 2025

Design thinking involves identification of challenges, getting inspired, ideation, experimentation as well as launch and learn of enterprises. According to Dada (2020), Dada and Asaolu (2023), and Babatunde (2024), entrepreneurship skills acquisition and upskilling can make the NextGen to develop entrepreneurial alertness to make contributions to industrial advancement. Other sources of entrepreneurial upskilling as claimed by the studentpreneurs were entrepreneurial mentorship and accelerator programme (90.24%); and personal entrepreneurial exploits/experience (86.54%). The least sources of entrepreneurial upskilling of the studentpreneurs were enterprise skill training (71.92%), enterprise start-up pitching competition (74.21%), entrepreneurship enlightenment programme (75.93%); and entrepreneurship development/enlightenment programme (82.44%). Babatunde (2024) argues that technical, financial, human, conceptual, and business management skills can influence the employability of undergraduates to acquire desired jobs. Similarly, Jackson et al. (2022) inform that enterprise capabilities as critical thinking and problem-solving, creativity and innovation, digital literacy, ethical behaviour, teamwork, and net-working skills are critical for graduates' effective shift to work.

4.6 Influence of Entrepreneurial Upskilling on Employment capability of the Studentpreneurs

Table 3 presents the output of regression analysis of how nine (9) independent variables of entrepreneurial upskilling positively and significantly influenced the employment capability of the studentpreneurs. The coefficients in Table 3 summarize the outputs of all the independent variables in the equation. The significant (p -value) column indicated that all the nine variables significantly contribute to the employment capability of the studentpreneurs. The outcome of the study revealed technology automation ($\beta = 2.028$, $p \leq 0.01$), entrepreneurship education and lifelong learning ($\beta = 2.173$, $p \leq 0.01$), collaboration/professional networking ($\beta = 1.466$, $p \leq 0.01$), design thinking ($\beta = 1.520$, $p \leq 0.05$), entrepreneurial mentorship and accelerator programme ($\beta = 0.708$, $p \leq 0.01$), personal entrepreneurial exploits/experience ($\beta = 1.852$, $p \leq 0.01$), entrepreneurship development/enlightenment programme ($\beta = 0.934$, $p \leq 0.01$), enterprise start-up pitching ($\beta = 0.691$, $p \leq 0.05$), enterprise skill training ($\beta = 0.645$, $p \leq 0.01$).

The findings indicate that entrepreneurial upskilling significantly enhances employment capability of studentpreneurs in Nigeria. This could be in the form of generation of new employment, establishment of new enterprise (entrepreneurship), develops a new idea with focus on innovation with access to employer's resources within the structure of an existing enterprise (intrapreneurship), improvement in product/service quality, creation of more market network/market share.

The study outcome is consistent with the view of Koko and Chimezie (2022), who found that technical skills prepare students for further training in industries and for advanced business courses. Moreover, such problem-solving skills give opportunities to utilize one's potential. The coefficient (Beta value) of the variables in Table 3 indicate how well each of the nine independent variables contributes to the regression outputs.

$$0.970 + 2.028TA + 2.173EELL + 1.466CPN + 1.520DT + 0.708EMAP + 1.852PEEE + 0.934E
DEP + 0.691ESP + 0.645EST$$

As revealed in Table 4, all the nine independent variables contributed an overall of $R^2 = 0.830$. This indicates that all the independent variables captured in this study contributed 83% to the employment capability of the studentpreneurs while the remaining 17% were contributed by other variables not captured in this study.

4.7 Upskilling and Employment capability of Studentpreneurs on the Local Economic Development

The influence of upskilling and employment capability of studentpreneurs of the Federal University of Technology, Akure, Nigeria on the local economic development is shown in Table 5. The table reveals that upskilling and employment capability of the studentpreneurs influence their generation of new employment/establishment of new enterprise, development of a new idea with focus on innovation with access to employers' resources within the structure of an existing enterprise (intrapreneurship), improvement in product/service quality, creation of more market network/market share, creation of wealth, creation of market network/market share, generation of environmentally friendly products alleviation of poverty, improve absorptive capacity, and rate of learning curve. This is in line with the findings of Bosman and Fernhaber (2018) among engineers in Switzerland.

Table 3: Multiple Regression of the Entrepreneurial Upskilling on Studentpreneurs' Employability Capability

Source of Entrepreneurial Upskilling	Coefficients (Beta-Value)	Standard Error	t-Value	Significance (P-Value)
Constant	0.970	0.663	0.865	0.396
Technology and Automation (TA, n=102)	2.028	0.402	1.557	0.000
Entrepreneurship Education and Lifelong Learning (EELL, n=101)	2.173	0.381	2.093	0.014
Collaboration Professional Networking (CPN, n=97)	1.466	0.501	3.189	0.019
Design Thinking (DT, n=96)	1.520	0.097	2.662	0.001
Entrepreneurial Mentorship and Accelerator Programme (EMAP, n=101)	0.708	0.214	2.901	0.016
Personal Entrepreneurial Exploits/Experience (PEEE, n=103)	1.852	0.842	2.117	0.007
Entrepreneurship Development/Enlightenment Programme (EDEP, n=91)	0.934	0.605	2.063	0.001
Enterprise Start-up Pitching (ESP, n=87)	0.691	0.506	1.712	0.023
Enterprise Skill Training (EST, n=98)	0.645	0.397	1.462	0.006

**Significant at 95 percent confidence level ($p \leq 0.05$)*

***Significant at 99 percent confidence level ($p < 0.01$)*

Table 4: Regression Model

R²	Adjusted R²	Std. Error of the Estimate	R²-Change	F-Change	Sig. F-Change
0.830	0.706	0.285	0.590	3.662	0.002

Table 5: Influence of Upskilling and Employment Capability of Studentpreneurs on the Local Economic Development

Influence of Upskilling and Employment capability	*Mean Rank
Generation of New Employment/Establishment of new enterprise	4.73 ^a
Development of new ideas and innovation within the structure of an existing enterprise	4.69 ^a
Improvement in product/service quality	4.58 ^a
Creation of more market network/market share	4.34 ^a
Creation of wealth	4.18 ^{ab}
Generation of environmentally friendly products	3.97 ^{ab}
Alleviation of poverty	3.86 ^b
Improved Absorptive Capacity/Rate of Learning Curve	3.66 ^b

Mean Rank: (1) Lowest Source – (5) Highest Source

Means with the same alphabets are not significantly different ($F=0.846, p \leq 0.01$)

*** Significant at 95% level of significance ($p < 0.05$); $R^2 = 0.741$ (74.1%)

Source: Studentpreneurs Survey, 2025

5.0 Conclusion and Policy Guidelines

This paper highlights the impact of years three to five studentpreneurs of the Federal University of Technology, Akure, Nigeria on local economic development. The research highlights how upskilling and employment capability of the studentpreneurs influence local economic development, providing suggestions for higher educational institutions and policymakers to

enhance entrepreneurship in Nigeria. The study establishes that the upskilling and employment capability positively and significantly affected enterprise activities of the students. These include generation of new employment through establishment of new enterprise, development of innovation with access to employers' resources, improvement in product and service qualities, creation of market networks as well as improving absorptive capacity and learning curve of the studentpreneurs. The study concludes that the technology and automation, entrepreneurship education and lifelong learning, collaboration/professional networking, design thinking, entrepreneurial mentorship and accelerator programme, personal entrepreneurial exploits/experience, entrepreneurship development/enlightenment programme; and enterprise start-up pitching offer a significant means to stimulate and enhance local economic development (LED).

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